

Analyzing Regional Variations in Air Quality: Insights from Indiana, Ohio, and Kentucky (2020–2024)

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Abstract

The rapid growth of urbanization and industrialization has intensified environmental challenges, with air pollution being among the most critical. It damages ecosystems, influences climate change, and poses severe health risks. This study focuses on the spatial air quality changes in Ohio, Indiana, and Kentucky over the period from 2020 to 2024 by analyzing key variables, including several air pollutants and meteorological conditions. Using Geographically Weighted Regression and Multiscale Geographically Weighted Regression methods, the study identifies regional differences in air quality and examines the primary contributing factors influencing these variations.

Key words: Air pollution, PM_{2.5}, GWR, MGWR

1. Introduction

The rapid growth of urbanization and industrialization has led to a variety of environmental challenges, among which air pollution is one of the most serious. Air pollution not only inflicts damage on ecosystems and affects climate change, but also impacts human health by triggering various medical problems, such as lung cancer, asthma, cardiovascular disease, and respiratory infections (Brauer et al., 2002). To measure air quality in a specific location, the Air Quality Index (AQI) is commonly used. The AQI combines measurements of various air pollutants collected by monitoring stations within specific areas. A higher AQI means a higher level of air pollution and worse air quality. Air pollution is the result of a combination of factors, and many different elements have been shown to influence it. One significant factor influencing air pollution is urbanization and the characteristics of the built environment (Wang et al., 2016). It is widely recognized that a higher traffic density contributes to increased levels of pollution, as vehicle emissions release a variety of harmful chemicals, including sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, and carbon compounds. Fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), which consists of tiny particles measuring 2.5 micrometers or less in diameter, is particularly concerning due to its severe impact on public health. In addition, sociodemographic factors, such as population density, also play a role in air pollution. As population density increases, so does energy consumption, resulting in more emissions and, consequently, higher pollution levels. Meteorological conditions, such as precipitation and wind, also play a crucial role in air pollution levels. In Birmingham, UK, a significant inverse relationship was observed between air pollution and the amount of daily precipitation. On the other hand, the wind can blow soil and road dust into the air, increasing air pollution levels (Vardoulakis and Kassomenos, 2008). Wind velocity also affects air quality, because high winds are helpful in dispersing and diluting air pollutants (Dawson et al., 2007).

Studies have increasingly applied various data analysis techniques to examine air quality and pollutant concentrations. In particular, spatial modeling approaches have been widely used to account for the geographic variation in air pollution data. Previous research has employed Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) to model air quality or PM_{2.5} concentrations, capturing spatial heterogeneity in environmental factors across different regions (Luo et al., 2017; Shen et al., 2022; Fotheringham et al., 2019; Shen et al., 2024). These studies demonstrate that spatially explicit models can provide a more accurate representation of local air pollution patterns than traditional global

models. In this study, we follow this approach by applying multiple regression frameworks to quantify the relationships between the Air Quality Index (AQI) and its explanatory variables. Specifically, we construct three models: a global regression model using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), a GWR model, and a Multiscale GWR (MGWR) model. The OLS model is a type of global statistic that assumes the relationship between the dependent and independent variables remains constant over space, providing a baseline for comparison with the spatially varying models.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the materials and methods. Section 3 is the results and discussion. In Section 4, Discussion and Concluding Remarks.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area and variables affecting air quality

The study focuses on the states of Ohio, Kentucky, and Indiana. Air quality data were collected from Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) monitoring stations across these states, including PM_{2.5} ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), PM₁₀ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), NO₂ (ppb), SO₂ (ppb), O₃ (ppm; daily maximum 8-hour average), and the Air Quality Index (AQI, 0–500). AQI values correspond to standard air quality categories: Good (0–50), Moderate (51–100), Unhealthy for Sensitive Groups (101–150), Unhealthy (151–200), Very Unhealthy (201–300), and Hazardous (301–500). Meteorological variables were also recorded, including outdoor temperature ($^{\circ}\text{F}$) and hourly resultant wind speed (kn). The data cover the period from 2020 to 2024.

Assuming seasonal effects on air quality, we developed four separate seasonal models corresponding to Winter (December–February), Spring (March–May), Summer (June–August), and Fall (September–November). For each season, pollutant and meteorological variables were averaged over the years 2020–2024 for each monitoring site. Then, County-level averages were computed for seasonal analyses.

Monitoring data availability varied by location due to station removals and new installations over the study period. Missing values were addressed using interpolation methods. Spatial interpolation of variables was performed using inverse distance weighting to generate continuous surfaces. Counties lacking direct EPA data were supplemented with at least two randomly placed points. A buffer was used around known points to control spatial smoothing, and the optimal inverse distance power was selected via leave-one-out cross-validation.

2.2. Regression models

To assess the global relationship between the dependent and independent variables we modeled data using the OLS method. The OLS model is defined as

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_k x_{ik} + \varepsilon_i, \quad (1)$$

where y_i is the dependent variable for observation i , x_{ik} represents the k th independent variable, β_0 is the intercept, β_k denotes the global regression coefficients (parameters), and ε_i is the random error term. In this global framework, the parameters β_k are assumed to be constant across all locations in the study area, implying that the spatial context does not influence the strength or direction of the relationships.

In contrast, GWR extends the traditional regression framework by allowing local rather than global parameters to be estimated (Fotheringham et al., 2001). As a local statistical technique, GWR captures spatial heterogeneity by producing a set of location-specific parameter estimates that reveal how relationships vary over space. The GWR model is expressed as

$$y_i = \beta_0(u_i, v_i) + \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_k(u_i, v_i) x_{ik} + \varepsilon_i, \quad (2)$$

where (u_i, v_i) are the spatial coordinates of location i , and $\beta_k(u_i, v_i)$ are the local regression coefficients estimated for that location. This formulation enables the model parameters to vary across space according to the local context, rather than remaining fixed as in the OLS model. The local parameter estimates in GWR are obtained using a spatial weighting scheme, which assigns weights to observations. The estimation of the local coefficients can be represented as

$$\hat{\beta}(u_i, v_i) = (X^T W(u_i, v_i) X)^{-1} X^T W(u_i, v_i) \mathbf{y}, \quad (3)$$

where X is the matrix of explanatory variables, \mathbf{y} is the vector of dependent variables, and $W(u_i, v_i)$ is a spatial weighting matrix that reflects the proximity of each observation to location (u_i, v_i) . Through this approach, GWR provides a nuanced understanding of spatially varying relationships that cannot be captured by traditional global models.

One of the important considerations in the GWR model is the determination of the spatial weighting matrix, which defines how observations contribute to the local parameter estimation. In this study, we used the bi-square kernel function to construct the weighting matrix. In the bi-square kernel, the weight of any data point located outside the specified bandwidth is set to zero. The bi-square weighting function is defined as

$$w_{ij} = \begin{cases} \left[1 - \left(\frac{d_{ij}}{b} \right)^2 \right]^2, & \text{if } |d_{ij}| < b, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where w_{ij} represents the weight assigned to the j th data point when estimating the local parameters at location i , d_{ij} is the Euclidean distance between the regression point i and the j th observation, and b denotes the bandwidth. The bandwidth parameter plays a crucial role in the performance of GWR models, as it determines the spatial extent of the local neighborhood influencing the regression.

Bandwidths can be specified either as fixed or adaptive. A fixed bandwidth remains constant for all regression points, while an adaptive bandwidth adjusts its size according to the spatial distribution of the data, becoming larger when observations are sparse and smaller when data points are dense. Based on the characteristics of our dataset, we used an adaptive bandwidth in this study. The optimal bandwidth was selected using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), ensuring a balance between model fit and complexity. It is also worth noting that larger bandwidths indicate less spatial variation in the estimated relationships, while smaller bandwidths capture more localized spatial heterogeneity.

We also employed the MGWR model in our study. The MGWR framework, proposed by Fotheringham et al. (2017), extends the standard GWR approach by allowing each explanatory variable to operate at its own spatial scale, rather than assuming a single bandwidth for all predictors. The MGWR model can be expressed as

$$y_i = \beta_0(u_i, v_i, b_0) + \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_k(u_i, v_i, b_k) x_{ik} + \varepsilon_i, \quad (5)$$

where y_i is the dependent variable for observation i , (u_i, v_i) represent the spatial coordinates of location i , x_{ik} is the k th independent variable, and $\beta_k(u_i, v_i, b_k)$ denotes the local regression coefficient for variable k at location (u_i, v_i) estimated using a bandwidth b_k . The term ε_i represents the random error.

In MGWR, each predictor variable is associated with its own adaptive bandwidth, which determines the spatial scale at which the variable influences the dependent variable. This flexibility allows MGWR to capture both local and global spatial processes within the same modeling framework. In this study, MGWR was implemented using adaptive bi-square kernel bandwidths for each predictor, and the optimal bandwidths were determined using the AIC. This approach enables more precise modeling of spatially varying relationships, as different explanatory variables may exhibit distinct spatial scales of influence.

2.3. Model performance evaluations

The performance of the global regression, GWR, and MGWR models was compared using several statistical criteria: the Corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc), the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC), the Residual Sum of Squares (RSS), and the adjusted coefficient of determination (R_{adj}^2). These measures provide a comprehensive assessment of model fit, explanatory power, and complexity.

The AICc was calculated as

$$\text{AICc} = 2n \ln(\hat{\sigma}) + n \ln(2\pi) + n \left(\frac{n + \text{tr}(S)}{n - 2 - \text{tr}(S)} \right), \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}$ is the estimated standard deviation of the residuals, n is the number of observations, and $\text{tr}(S)$ is the trace of the hat matrix representing model complexity. Lower AICc values indicate better model performance after accounting for the number of parameters.

The BIC was computed as

$$\text{BIC} = n \ln(\text{RSS}/n) + k \ln(n), \quad (7)$$

where RSS is the residual sum of squares and k is the number of model parameters. Similar to AICc, smaller BIC values denote better model fit while imposing a stronger penalty for model complexity.

The RSS is given by

$$\text{RSS} = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2, \quad (8)$$

where y_i and \hat{y}_i represent the observed and predicted values, respectively. A smaller RSS indicates a closer fit between the model and the observed data.

Finally, the adjusted coefficient of determination, which accounts for the number of predictors, was calculated as

$$R_{\text{adj}}^2 = 1 - \frac{(1 - R^2)(n - 1)}{n - k - 1}, \quad (9)$$

where R^2 is the coefficient of determination, n is the number of observations, and k is the number of explanatory variables. Higher values of R_{adj}^2 indicate a stronger explanatory capability of the model after adjusting for model complexity.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Annual variation in pollutant concentrations in three states

Table 1 presents state-wise summary statistics of the AQI for Indiana, Kentucky, and Ohio across the four seasons. For each state and season, the table reports the maximum, minimum, mean, standard deviation, and median AQI values. This summary highlights seasonal variations in air quality, showing that AQI tends to be highest during the summer in all three states and lowest during the fall for Kentucky and Indiana, and winter for Ohio. Figure 1 shows the variation of AQI and all the independent variables.

3.2. Model performance

The GWR and MGWR models were fitted using the `GWmodel` package in R (Lu et al., 2014), which provides a comprehensive framework for geographically weighted modeling and spatial analysis. For the GWR and MGWR models, the optimal bandwidths were determined and are presented in Table 2. In the GWR model, the same bandwidth is applied to all variables, whereas in the MGWR model, each variable is assigned its own bandwidth. Larger bandwidths indicate less spatial variation in the estimated relationships. For instance, the temperature variable exhibits relatively larger bandwidths in the summer and winter MGWR models, suggesting less spatial variation between

Figure 1: Seasonal spatial distribution of AQI, key air pollutants (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃), temperature, and wind during Spring, Summer, Fall, and Winter. The maps depict seasonal variations and spatial heterogeneity in air quality and meteorological conditions across the study area.

Table 1: State-wise AQI summary statistics across all four seasons

State	Season	Max	Min	Mean	Standard deviation	Median
Indiana	Spring	60.4	33.6	44.9	6.6	42.6
	Summer	71.2	41.7	53.1	7.4	53.8
	Fall	62.3	29.5	41.5	7.9	39.5
	Winter	75.0	23.4	40.7	11.8	42.2
Kentucky	Spring	54.5	37.5	43.9	3.9	43.8
	Summer	68.5	16.4	47.9	9.2	47.8
	Fall	53.8	14.0	38.7	8.8	39.0
	Winter	56.3	24.5	40.6	8.2	41.2
Ohio	Spring	66.0	9.2	44.1	10.2	45.3
	Summer	79.7	13.5	52.7	12.7	54.2
	Fall	63.0	3.0	39.4	10.9	38.6
	Winter	61.4	8.99	42.2	12.9	44.0

temperature and AQI during these seasons. In contrast, variables like SO_2 and Wind have smaller bandwidths, reflecting their more localized influences.

Table 2: Bandwidth selection for GWR and MGWR

Season	Bandwidth							
	GWR		MGWR					
	All	$\text{PM}_{2.5}$	PM_{10}	NO_2	SO_2	O_3	Temp	Wind
Spring	60	35	100	68	11	21	48	45
Summer	48	136	25	83	45	68	162	44
Fall	34	19	17	49	61	42	25	18
Winter	60	79	11	61	165	71	156	44

The OLS regression model was constructed with AQI as the response variable and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , NO_2 , SO_2 , and O_3 as predictors. All predictors were found to be significant at the 5% level. The GWR and MGWR models were fitted using the same set of predictors. Since OLS, GWR, and MGWR models were all developed in this study, the advantages of the GWR models over the OLS model can be evaluated by comparing their AICc, BIC, and adjusted R^2 values. The results are given in Table 3. In the Spring and Summer models, the MGWR model yielded the lowest AICc and BIC values, while in the Winter model, the GWR model produced the minimum AICc and BIC. For the Fall model, both GWR and MGWR showed nearly identical AIC values and the same adjusted R^2 .

Summary statistics of the OLS, GWR, and MGWR model coefficients are given in Tables 4, 5, and 6, respectively. The maps of the spatial variation of $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , and O_3 coefficient estimate, with significant areas highlighted are given in Figures 2, 3, and 4. Table 4 presents the global regression coefficient estimates across seasons, with standard errors shown in parentheses. The global model captures overall, non-spatial associations between air pollutants, meteorological variables, and the response variable. Across all seasons, $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , NO_2 , and O_3 show positive associations, while SO_2 and Wind generally show small or negative effects. O_3 exhibits the largest effect magnitude, particularly in Spring (1987.2 ± 558.8), indicating its strong influence on the outcome. Meteorological variables such as Temperature and Wind have relatively minor impacts in the global model. Overall, the global regression provides a baseline understanding of the average effect of each predictor without accounting for spatial variability.

To address this limitation, the GWR model was applied, allowing each coefficient to vary spatially. The GWR results in Table 5 reveal significant spatial heterogeneity in predictor effects across counties and seasons. Coefficients for $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} remain generally positive, but local estimates vary substantially, with extremes exceeding the global effect. O_3 shows particularly strong spatial variation in Spring and Fall, reflecting localized impacts that the global model cannot capture. Meteorological variables retain small magnitudes but demonstrate noticeable spatial variability, especially in Fall. Compared with the global model, GWR highlights the importance of accounting for local differences, showing that the strength and even direction of associations can vary across space.

The MGWR model further refines this analysis by allowing each variable to operate at its own spatial scale (Table 6). Compared with GWR, MGWR smooths out the extreme local fluctuations by using variable-specific bandwidths (Table 2). For example, $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} maintain positive associations across all seasons, but their effects are more stable and less locally extreme.

Table 3: Model comparison across seasons

Global				
Season	AICc	BIC	AdjR ²	RSS
Spring	1345	1129	0.323	1462
Summer	1427	1211	0.556	1918
Fall	1311	1095	0.487	1305
Winter	1434	1218	0.379	1965
GWR				
Spring	1187	1095	0.688	503
Summer	1214	1146	0.841	483
Fall	1113	1079	0.840	251
Winter	1346	1244	0.628	899
MGWR				
Spring	1027	1000	0.864	165
Summer	1198	1095	0.831	553
Fall	1117	1087	0.840	239
Winter	1375	1321	0.629	747

Spatial distribution of residuals from the GWR and MGWR models across four seasons is given in Figure 5. Red areas indicate overestimation, while blue areas represent underestimation. The maps highlight spatial patterns in model performance, showing that the models produce more spatially random residuals, suggesting improved model fits and reduced spatial autocorrelation. To numerically assess spatial autocorrelation in the residuals of the GWR and MGWR models, we applied Moran’s I test. The results indicated no spatial autocorrelation, as Moran’s I was close to zero. Moreover, the test p-value was closer to 1. Furthermore, the actual and predicted value plots are given in Figure 6. Overall, the MGWR model demonstrated better performance in modeling air quality.

4. Discussion and concluding remarks

Overall, the results demonstrate that incorporating spatial heterogeneity substantially improves model performance compared with the global regression approach. The GWR model revealed notable local variations in the effects of air pollutants and meteorological factors on AQI, while the MGWR model provided an even more refined understanding by allowing each variable to operate at its own spatial scale. The comparison of AICc, BIC, and adjusted R^2 values confirmed that MGWR generally outperformed both the OLS and GWR models, indicating its superior ability to capture complex

Table 4: Global model coefficient estimates across seasons. Parentheses indicate the standard error.

Season	Intercept	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁₀	NO ₂	SO ₂	O ₃	Temp	Wind
Spring	-42.4 (27.6)	3.4 (0.5)	1.0 (0.2)	0.3 (0.3)	-0.1 (0.2)	1987.2 (558.8)	0.1 (0.1)	-0.5 (0.1)
Summer	-41.4 (16.3)	1.7 (0.5)	1.4 (0.2)	1.3 (0.3)	0.3 (0.3)	556.3 (108.5)	0.2 (0.1)	-0.2 (0.1)
Fall	-24.4 (18.1)	2.1 (0.4)	1.0 (0.1)	0.7 (0.2)	0.4 (0.2)	631.0 (202.7)	-0.0 (0.2)	-0.1 (0.1)
Winter	8.3 (14.6)	2.1 (0.5)	1.7 (0.3)	1.1 (0.4)	-0.2 (0.5)	361.1 (88.8)	-0.3 (0.1)	-0.3 (0.1)

Table 5: GWR model coefficient summary statistics across seasons

Statistic	Intercept	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁₀	NO ₂	SO ₂	O ₃	Temp	Wind
Spring								
Min	-556.6	-2.8	-3.0	-6.2	-6.6	-5771.6	-5.8	-6.0
Q1	-51.3	1.9	-0.1	-0.3	-1.7	-817.2	-0.6	-1.0
Median	28.2	3.0	0.6	0.5	-0.5	663.2	-0.2	-0.1
Mean	97.6	4.9	1.1	1.5	0.1	3019.2	0.4	0.2
Q3	535.4	17.0	3.2	5.8	3.7	7049.1	2.0	5.4
Max	535.4	17.0	3.2	5.8	3.7	7049.1	2.0	5.4
Summer								
Min	-795.2	-7.7	-7.1	-13.0	-8.1	-1269.1	-2.3	-5.5
Q1	-153.8	-0.4	0.5	-1.0	-0.4	648.4	-0.8	-0.3
Median	-72.8	1.6	1.1	0.2	0.5	1346.7	-0.2	0.0
Mean	20.7	3.1	2.4	2.2	2.1	1951.7	0.7	0.6
Q3	552.7	8.6	14.3	15.1	8.5	1917.5	3.8	6.5
Max	552.7	8.6	14.3	15.1	8.5	3566.8	3.8	6.5
Fall								
Min	-2903.5	-35.6	-8.7	-9.5	-13.9	-10120	-11.9	-11.1
Q1	-245.7	0.1	0.1	-0.6	-1.7	-1715.7	-1.6	-0.9
Median	-33.4	2.6	1.1	0.3	-0.4	-110.6	0.5	-0.1
Mean	152.5	4.4	2.3	1.5	1.2	1730.6	3.7	0.6
Q3	2001.3	28.4	5.6	13.0	24.7	18542.3	22.7	14.4
Max	2001.3	28.4	5.6	13.0	24.7	18542.3	22.7	14.4
Winter								
Min	-928.8	-5.3	-11.7	-16.9	-22.8	-2413.2	-1.7	-4.3
Q1	-48.5	2.3	-0.5	-0.2	-4.0	-44.8	-0.5	-0.7
Median	-4.8	3.6	0.8	1.0	-1.2	316.7	-0.1	-0.2
Mean	79.6	5.4	1.7	3.0	0.9	560.7	0.3	0.1
Q3	749.2	17.3	9.4	16.8	18.4	2151.1	1.2	5.9
Max	749.2	17.3	9.4	16.8	18.4	2151.1	1.2	5.9

Table 6: MGWR model coefficient summary statistics across seasons

Statistic	Intercept	PM _{2.5}	PM ₁₀	NO ₂	SO ₂	O ₃	Temp	Wind
Spring								
Min	-318.0	-0.4	0.1	-0.1	-14.5	-8536.8	-4.1	-3.3
Q1	-59.2	1.9	0.3	0.3	-3.4	-1549.3	-0.5	-1.0
Median	40.5	3.3	0.6	0.6	-1.9	670.7	-0.3	-0.5
Mean	30.3	4.1	0.7	0.8	-2.1	955.0	-0.4	-0.6
Q3	141.7	5.0	1.1	0.9	-0.7	3691.0	-0.2	0.2
Max	282.1	13.3	1.4	3.8	18.5	11913.5	0.8	2.8
Summer								
Min	-318.2	0.8	-4.0	-0.7	-3.0	-46.8	-1.0	-1.3
Q1	-141.5	1.1	0.5	0.4	-0.8	563.3	-0.6	-0.3
Median	-63.7	1.6	1.3	1.2	0.0	1219.5	-0.1	0.1
Mean	-73.1	1.7	1.3	1.7	0.1	1051.2	-0.3	0.3
Q3	-4.1	2.1	2.1	2.9	0.6	1569.5	0.0	0.7
Max	132.1	3.1	5.2	5.4	5.6	1917.5	0.1	2.9
Fall								
Min	-907.6	-1.6	-2.1	-1.5	-2.5	-2497.2	-6.4	-2.4
Q1	-148.6	1.0	0.0	-0.6	-0.9	32.1	-1.5	-0.6
Median	-37.6	3.5	1.6	-0.3	-0.2	536.0	0.3	-0.2
Mean	-71.4	3.9	1.8	-0.3	0.0	674.3	0.7	-0.1
Q3	81.2	6.9	3.7	0.1	0.1	1707.7	1.4	0.4
Max	356.5	11.9	4.6	1.0	5.0	3758.9	13.4	3.1
Winter								
Min	-228.4	-1.1	-11.2	-0.7	-1.5	-887.6	-0.4	-1.7
Q1	-69.1	1.2	0.5	0.8	-1.2	231.5	-0.2	-0.5
Median	-22.7	2.5	1.9	1.7	-0.2	306.5	0.0	-0.2
Mean	-23.2	2.2	2.3	1.8	-0.3	247.6	-0.1	-0.3
Q3	22.6	3.4	4.5	2.3	0.4	446.6	0.1	0.1
Max	235.9	6.2	15.4	8.3	1.8	744.4	0.1	1.3

Figure 2: Spatial distribution of the $PM_{2.5}$ regression coefficient significance across four seasons (Spring, Summer, Fall, and Winter) for both GWR and MGWR models. Areas highlighted indicate regions where the $PM_{2.5}$ coefficient is statistically significant.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of the PM_{10} regression coefficient significance across four seasons (Spring, Summer, Fall, and Winter) for both GWR and MGWR models. Areas highlighted indicate regions where the PM_{10} coefficient is statistically significant.

Figure 4: Spatial distribution of the O_3 regression coefficient significance across four seasons (Spring, Summer, Fall, and Winter) for both GWR and MGWR models. Areas highlighted indicate regions where the O_3 coefficient is statistically significant.

Figure 5: Spatial distribution of residuals from the GWR and MGWR models across four seasons (Spring, Summer, Fall, and Winter). Red areas indicate overestimation, while blue areas represent underestimation.

spatial relationships. Furthermore, the MGWR residuals showed minimal spatial autocorrelation, suggesting that the model successfully explained most of the spatial structure in the data.

However, several limitations should be acknowledged. The dataset contained missing values, which may have introduced uncertainty in the estimated coefficients despite data cleaning and pre-processing. Additionally, the study was limited to air pollutants and meteorological variables. Future analyses could be enhanced by integrating other spatial and temporal factors such as traffic density, land use characteristics, industrial emission sources, population density, and topographic information. Incorporating these variables could improve the model's explanatory power and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the spatial drivers of air quality variations. Despite these limitations, the findings highlight the value of spatially explicit modeling approaches like GWR and MGWR for environmental and public health research.

Figure 6: Seasonal predicted values of $PM_{2.5}$ across Spring, Summer, Fall, and Winter for the Global, GWR, and MGWR models.

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